

Nodes Centrality in Urban Road Network, Aizawl City with Network Centrality Measures

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Abstract : This paper attempts to develop quantitative measures of node (junction) centrality in urban road network located in hill area using centrality measures for node centrality. The paper focuses on identification of critical nodes over the networks, proving an idea that 'some points are more important than others because they are more central'. The study also adopted geospatial technology to present and analyze the spatial distribution of node centrality in Aizawl city. The results from this analysis can be used to develop urban road network design guidelines that can be used to address current transportation problems and socio-economic development.

Keywords : Centrality Measures, Geospatial Technology, Spatial Distribution of Nodes Centrality, Correlation of Centrality

The interaction of one space to another in a certain degree at a definite stage creates a complex network system and forms an intricate spatial organization. The notion of centrality is resolute by the arrangement of network at certain level over the space. The science of network and its mathematical tools have been providing ambiguous results for measurements of centrality in the fields of social science, spatial science, economic, and biological science etc. The idea of centrality in social science was firstly proposed by Bavelas who hypothesized the structural centrality and influence on communication in a small group (Bavelas 1948).

Network structure and topology inherently determine the efficiency

of node accessibility, which is the product of movement pattern, direction and flow pattern etc. Simply, topology and structure of network affect attributes of the node and edge centrality. In larger picture, the concept of centrality exposes role and identity of the node and edges in the network system, considering the nodes existed in the network as common resources, which is accessible from any point through edges. In this context, the network system represents the mode of communications and node is recognized as the center of diffusion. Also central place refers to node which has a relative surplus of meaning due to its fulfillment of central functions for the surrounding areas (Christaller 1933).

The characterizations of

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complex network systems using statistical and computational techniques have attracted considerable attentions in literature in recent years. Complex systems are composed of numerous components; interacting in such a manner that collective behavior is no longer an ordinal function of their individual behaviors. Centrality is the principal properties in a complex network system that transformed the surrounding geographical space in a form of point, linear and spatial centrality. Similarly, node, linear and spatial centrality is a dynamic concept and not mutually exclusive, that differs from one perspective to another at different stages. The centrality possibly determines the attributes of the node or some attributes relatively stronger than those of the other spatial units in the region. It may also be considered to possess strong centrality, and this centrality is based on scale of attributes (Li *et al.* 2017). Considerably, the centrality of a node is determined by its attributes and the distance from other nodes, based on geographical proximity and distance from the spatial unit.

Earlier studies on urban network are mostly confined on the shortest pathway analysis minimizing the time and cost of movement (Yang and Sam 1995, Girvan and Newman 2002, Holme 2003). The different form of study emerged as emphasis on the

resilience of transportation networks, to model the traffic flow between municipalities, clusters and commuters perception (Guimer *et al.* 2005, Boccaletti *et al.* 2006, Scheurer and Porta 2008, Berche *et al.* 2009). Recently, the paradigm of urban network study shifted towards centrality measures. Centrality represents the fundamental concept; if one look into the role and identities of central nodes. Centrality measures are essential for the conception of node identities, node attributes, network structural attributers and network topological attribute. Centrality or central places appear to have spatial privileges that habitat communities further luxuriate in transportation and socio-economic amenities or facilities. Recently the emphasis is shifted to the distribution of centrality values through all nodes (Crucitti *et al.* 2006).

In urban network entity, road transport network plays a pivotal role in the complex urban networking system. Transport networks support the efficiency of movement of the people and goods at various directions and also accessibly of each node in the chain of network. The study of urban network implies the distribution of centrality and its attributes over the space in different dimensions and argued that some places are more important than others because they are more central (Wilson 2000). The

study primarily focuses on centrality measures for analysis of nodes, spatial distributions and arrangement of nodes which have a significant role for local and global attraction.

Materials and Methods :

Materials and methods of study are primarily divided on three main steps namely, database design, network centrality measures and applications of geospatial technology.

Database Design :

The road network was obtained from Aizawl city, located in Aizawl district of Mizoram. This city is situated on the top of Aizawl range, the topography of the region makes the arrangement of road networking system more complicated. Extraction of network data set is an important task for database design. It is extracted from open-source data domain like Google Earth and Open-Street Map. The extracted data are employed for generations of nodes and edges in the study area. The extracted roads and junctions were transformed and converted from .kml to .shp file to performed further manipulations and analysis, with the help of suitable GIS techniques. In this study, street intersections represent nodes and linear connections turn into edges. The whole network comprises of 183 junctions (nodes/vertex) and 242 streets (edges) segments in this network. Each of the roads and

junctions were checked and modified for limiting topological error. Further, Toposheet No. 84 A/9, 84 A/10 and 84 A/14, issued by Survey of India 1990 and Aizawl Municipal Road Map is also integrated for the accuracy assessment and ground thought verifications in doubtful areas. For further analysis the extracted data are stored in ArcGIS database.

Centrality Measures :

The study employed network centrality measures for examining each point on the network which is directly or indirectly associated with the road network topology and network arrangement. The centrality of a place is that component of its functional magnitude (Christaller 1933). In this case, nodes represent functional phenomena, the street junctions where two or more streets intersect represented node and denoting edges as street segments. The method used for this study is solely based on simple directed graph, and the adjacency matrix was developed to measure point centrality. The centrality of each node was calculated based on the mathematical equations using the centrality measures; Degree of Centrality (C_D), Closeness Centrality (C_C), Betweenness Centrality (C_B) and Eigenvector Centrality (C_E) are calculated. Further to provide lucid result, comprehensive spatial distributions of nodes centrality are graphically represented by making

use of geospatial analysis software. The study analyzed the spatial distribution of node centrality and changes therein to visualize the changing pattern of centrality in general and in order to identify the important nodes. Classificatory approach is adopted to describe the changes of centrality pattern. The calculated values of centrality measures are classified into five centrality classes based on natural break method (Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4). The study adopted GEPHI network analysis software for the centrality calculation and ArcGis 10.3 software is employed for spatial analysis.

Result Definitions and Analysis :

In degree of centrality every connected node has some degree of centrality. On the other hand, a node is more important rather than the others if it is linked with other important nodes. Centrality measures depicted the hierarchical arrangement of the points and network structure.

Degree of Centrality :

The degree of centrality is a simple mathematical representation of the degree of point on concept of adjacency matrix (Niemiens 1974, Freeman 1979). Degree of centrality is the idea that important nodes have the largest number of ties to other nodes in the graph (Porta et al. 2006). This measurement is widely adopted for centrality measures, directly related to the

neighborhood and considered as local measured (Koschutzki et al. 2005, Tisiotas and Polyzos 2013, Jayaweera et al. 2017). The degree of centrality (C_D) is expressed as;

$$C_D = \frac{1}{|V| - 1} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} a_{ij} = \frac{deg(i)}{N - 1} \dots 1$$

where, $|V| = N$ represents the number of vertices, i the reference node, a_{ij} the number of the adjacent edges that originate from a node and $deg(i)$ the degree of a node. In this analysis, the degree of centrality ranges from two to ten degree in the entire network. The degree with 2 degree of centrality represented lowest degree of intersection, which has limited direct connection through the surrounding nodes. The high degree of centrality likes 10 (Bawngkawn, Vaivakawn and ITI junction), 9 (Dakinpui and Sikulpuikawn junction), and 8 (Kulikawn, Ramhlu North, Khatla and Saikhamakawn junction etc.) are more attractive than low scoring nodes (Fig. 1). The degree of centrality is influenced by the local and it doesn't depict its position in the entire network.

Closeness Centrality :

The centrality of a point measured by summing the geodesic distances from one point to all other points in the graph is called closeness centrality (Sabidussi 1966). Closeness centrality quantifies to what extent a node (i) is close to all of the other nodes along the shortest paths of the network

(Wang *et al.* 2018). Closeness centrality evaluates centrality through geodesic distance from a given vertex to all the other vertices and assess to which extent a selected vertex *i* is close to all the other vertices along the geodesic

paths (Tisiotas and Polyzos 2013). Then, the Closeness centrality (C_c) is expressed as;

$$C_c = \frac{N - 1}{\sum_{i=1; j \neq 1}^N d_{ij}} \dots 2$$

where, *N* is the total number of

Figure 1: Spatial Distribution of Degree of Centrality (C_D)

nodes in the network, d_{ij} is the shortest path length between node i and j . The study revealed closeness centrality of nodes ranging from 0.078105 to 0.147224. In the entire network Laipuitlang junction score the lowest closeness centrality which means the junction represented the isolated nodes

amongst the entire nodes. Bazar Bungkawn junction is the highest closeness centrality. Based on the calculated value, Vaivakawn (0.142412), Chhingaveng (0.143192) and SaronVeng (0.146988) nodes are also the easiest accessible nodes with shortest path from each of the nodes (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Spatial Distribution of Closeness (CC)

Betweenness Centrality :

In the network system, some of the nodes are more central rather than spatial distance, subject to their positions. A node that falls on the communication paths between other nodes exhibits a potential for control of their communication (Freeman 1979). Betweenness describes the influence of the nodes in the network on the transmission of information and belongs to the global features of the network (Wang and Fu 2017). The shortest edge distances between all pairs of vertices in the network are considered in this equation (Batista and Bazzan 2015). This equation defines the significance of node location in the network system, which corresponds to influence and control on the other. The same principle is also applied by scholars, Wasserman and Faust 1994, Crucitti et al. 2006, Oluwajana et al. 2012, Jayaweera et al. 2017 and Wang et al. 2018 etc., the following equation explained Betweenness Centralit (C_B);

$$C_B = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t \in V} \frac{d(s,t|v)}{d(s,t)} \dots 3$$

where, $d(s,t|v)$ is the number of shortest paths between s and t passing through node v and, $d(s,t)$ is the total number of shortest paths between s and t . According to the calculated results, betweenness centrality ranges from 0 to 3.937. In the entire network, 30 nodes

scored 0 betweenness centrality, meaning they are irrelevant to commute each other. The scores of betweenness centrality ranging from 0 to 3.937. The low scoring nodes are positioned at the fringes of network like Sihphir, Zuangtui, Zemabawk and Maubawk etc. Meanwhile, high scoring nodes like, Bazar Bungkawn(3.937782), SaronVeng (3.851355) Vaivakawn (3.852721), and Bawngkawn (3.784672) play a significant role to control flow of information in the network (Fig. 3).

Eigenvector Centrality :

Eigenvector centrality measures the centrality of a node in a network based on the weighted sum of centralities of its neighbors (Jayaweera et al. 2017). In this measure, localized factors and surrounding nodes intuitively determine the eigenvector centrality. It defines the importance of a node through its connectivity to important nodes. The centrality of a vertex is proportional to the sum of the centralities of the vertices to which it is connected (Turker 2018). The following equation describes Eigenvector centrality (C_E);

$$\lambda x = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} x_j \dots 3$$

where, A be the adjacency matrix for this graph; $a_{ij} = 1$ if vertices i and j are connected by an edge and 0 if not, $Ax = \lambda x$, $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then, λ denote the largest

eigenvalue of A and n is the number of vertices (Bonacich 2007). This calculation assessed Dakinpui junction as the highest eigenvector with 1 degree of eigenvalue, followed by Saikhamakawn (0.932691),

Kulikawn (0.874130) and Sikulpuikawn (0.847242). The lowest eigenvector is represented by Laipuitlang (0.043440) and Zemabawk (0.065758) junctions (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: Spatial Distribution of Betweenness Centrality (C_B)

Spatial Analysis of Nodes Distribution :

Geographic Information System (GIS) allowed us to represent spatial distributions of nodes over the space; which is very crucial for representing nodes centrality pattern and identification of crucial nodes in the entire network system. Natural classification scheme is accomplished to maximize the variance between classes and minimize the variance within classes (Lin, 2013). The five color-coded schemes are applied in this study, representing five classes of node centrality - Very High, High, Medium, Low and Very Low centrality.

The nodes having Very High C_D (0.778152 - 1.000000) are located along the main axial roads (edge between Bawngkawn to Kulikawn) and, mainly confined in the central part of the network. Bawngkawn, Ramhlun North Bazar Bungkawn, Dakinpui, and Kulikawn junctions are important nodes in this network. Generally, Very High values C_D are arranged in linear pattern due to the influence of geographical factors on the arrangement of road network. High values of C_D (0.698971 - 0.778151) are scattered around the entire network and intertwined with Very High C_D . Very low centrality nodes (<0.301030) represent dead-end connection, mainly located in the outskirts of the network (Fig.1).

The distribution of nodes with Very High (0.128242 - 0.147224)

and High (0.116118 - 0.128241) C_C are significantly associated with the entire network. Figure 2 highlighted the very high and high scoring nodes confluent on the axial roads and central region of the network. Moderate (0.104334 - 0.116117) C_C class is diverging out from the center towards north, south and east direction. Thus, western section and portion of the northern part of the network is associated with Low (0.093226 - 0.104333) and Very Low (0.078105 - 0.093225) C_C classes. The figure illustrated the eastern portion of the network more highly accessible than the western section of the network, meaning each of the nodes is closer and nearer (Fig. 2).

The nodes with High (3.297037 - 3.937782) C_B are mainly scattered all over the network. There are mainly concentrated in Bawngkawn, Chanmari, Vaivakawn and Khatla. Among these the most influential node is Bazar Bungkawn with 3.93778. Figure 3 shows that the eastern half of the network is dominated by Very High C_B node and is the result of the existence of World Bank road in the eastern section of the network. It has significant influence on distribution of C_B over eastern part of the network. Similarly, the western part of the network is governed by High (2.776846 - 3.297036) and Moderate (1.990488 - 2.776845) C_B . The least influential nodes, Low (0.000001 - 1.990487) and Very Low

(< 0.000001) C_B are scattered north and eastern slopes of the network (Fig. 3).

Very High (0.644876 - 1.000000) C_E category occupied central part of the network and the northern and southern tip of the network. High C_E (0.484198 - 0.644875) nodes are also arranged in longitudinal direction along with the edges. The southern and western part of the network is dominated by Moderate C_E (0.354991 - 0.484197) nodes. In this network, Low (0.213293 - 0.354990) and Very Low C_E (0.043440 - 0.213292) scoring nodes are frequently found on northern and eastern section (Fig. 4).

Correlation of Centrality Measures :

The correlation coefficient of centrality measures specified in the study has positive correlation in case of urban network in Aizawl city. It is clear to argue that centrality measures are closely associated with node centrality. Table 1 depicted that centrality measures are positive correlation with each other. But, in the presented network system some of the centrality measures are more associated than the other. For example, the relationship between

C_D and C_B accounts for 0.870, between C_D and C_E has 0.769 of positive relationship. Thus, vertices with higher degree of centrality tend to have high betweenness and eigenvector centrality. The lowest degree of correlation is observed between C_D and C_C (0.391), which signifies that C_D has less significance for C_C or vice versa. The coefficient of correlation illustrated as C_C has least amount of significance over the C_B and C_E having 0.512 and 0.420 correlation respectively (Table -1).

Conclusion :

The study signifies that the different concepts and measures of centrality are appropriate for identification and analysis of the node centrality. It provides the reliability of directed graph concept and construction of adjacency matrix for node centrality measures and network analysis, thus, proving that different centrality measures C_D , C_C , C_B and C_E provide different nature of centrality. GIS technology is proved to be a useful and efficient tool for spatial data management and manipulation. The study identified geographical, historical, economic and social factors as

Table - 1: Correlation Coefficient of Centrality Measures

Degree	CD	CC	CB	CE
CD	1			
CC	0.391	1		
CB	0.87	0.512	1	
CE	0.769	0.420	0.598	1

important factors for existence of road network which are very crucial for location of nodes centrality and they also determined the quantity of node centrality. Nodes centrality explains the nature of geographical centrality, namely, global, local, isolated unit of centrality. For example, all the Very High and High centrality value nodes are confined to the central part of the network excluding C_B . It means the nodes laying the central parts of the network is more influential and have ability to control flow of information throughout the network system rather than those nodes laying in the outer part of the network. The result of this study revealed C_D , C_B and C_E as significantly correlated in network centrality measures. The integration of centrality measures and GIS technology provide the graphical presentation of centrality measures which is very crucial for identification of important nodes and spatial distributions of nodes. Very High D_C and D_E are distributed in longitudinal fashion which is influenced by the arrangement of the edges. The study found out less influential nodes, Low and Very Low degree classes are located in irregular fashion, which means the low scoring nodes are diverse in nature due to the influence of the local and global factors. For further work, the present study can be extended to cover spatial centrality analysis through node and edges centrality analysis which is not

covered in this study. Above that, more detailed node and edges density analysis can also be taken up via GIS and image processing techniques to arrive at relevant result.

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